

**You met your favorite
superhero/ superheroine.**

**You heard that your cousin
was ill.**

You had an invitation to a party you do not want to go to.

**You got a low grade in a
school test.**

**You won in a competition /
race.**

**You realized that a friend of
yours was lying to you.**

**Your parents punished you
by withdrawing one of your
favorite toys for a week.**

You could fly.

**You lost the toy that a friend
had lent you.**

**You found a mouse in your
room.**

**Your godfather / godmother
gave you a birthday present
that you did not like.**

**You heard your father
saying how proud he is of
you.**

**You saw a homeless man
sleeping on the square
bench.**

You managed to do a household on your own for the first time, such as cooking, cleaning etc.

**Your brother / sister
shared a secret with you.**

**Your best friend moved to
another city.**

**You saw someone
entering your neighbor's
house through the window.**

**You broke mom's favorite
jar.**

**You found a 50 euro
banknote in the park.**

**Someone offered you food
that you did not like.**

**You were suddenly 10 years
older.**

**You lost your suitcase at
the airport.**

**You could make a wish
come true.**

**You found a machine that
travels you through time.**

**A friend asked your opinion
on his / her new haircut,
which you did not like.**

**You became Prime Minister
for a week.**

**Your pet had no appetite for
food and play.**

**You could not find the
Maths book just before
going to school.**

**The boy / girl you liked did
not show any interest in
you.**

**Your party did not take
place because you got sick
the day before.**

You won 1 million euros.